

AN INVESTIGATION INTO LAND USE DYNAMICS IN MAHARASHTRA – AN ECOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Land, a vital natural resource, is indispensable for both agricultural and non-agricultural purposes. This includes establishing housing, industries, roads, parks, railway lines, and various commercial ventures. Development endeavours often require significant land allocation, raising concerns about potential encroachment on agricultural land, particularly fertile rural areas. Examining how land-use patterns evolve over time allows for deliberate and well-planned land management. In this context, a study was conducted to investigate land use dynamics and their ecological implications in Maharashtra, utilizing time series secondary data of 57 years from 1960-61 to 2016-17. The ecological implications of various land use categories were assessed using the method of annual rate of change. The entire period was decomposed into two periods, viz., Period-I (Pre-liberalization), Period-II (Post-liberalization). The primary focus was to assess the ecological impact of these land use changes in Maharashtra. Inter-sectoral budgeting for Period-I and Period-II indicates that, in Maharashtra state, though the area under ecological sector declined in both the periods, the rate of decline was more (15123 ha/annum) in Period-II than that in Period-I (213 ha/annum). Ecological implications of land use dynamics in Maharashtra revealed that area shift under desirable ecology compared to undesirable ecology has not been favourable in Period-II, where land-use shift has been occurring from the desirable ecology towards agricultural and non-agricultural sectors. The shift of area from desirable to undesirable ecological sector may have long term negative environmental implications. So, integration of agricultural and rural development programmes viz; National Horticulture Mission, National Bamboo Mission, MNREGA etc. are necessary to make the use of barren and uncultivable land for cultivation, for holistic rural development, natural resource management and eco-restoration.

Keywords- ecological implications, pre-liberalization, post-liberalization, annual rate of change, desirable ecology, undesirable ecology.

Introduction

Agriculture plays a noteworthy role in Indian economy and continues to be one of the most vibrant sectors ensuring food security to the country. The economic contribution of agriculture to India's GDP is steadily declining with the country's broad-based economic growth. Still, agriculture is demographically the broadest economic sector and plays a significant role in the overall socio-economic fabric of India and it continues to provide gainful employment and livelihood to majority of the population. Primarily, agriculture is a land-based activity and as such, land and water are the crucial natural resources for any development activity. Consequently, access to land and control over its uses were the prime sources of conflict within and between communities throughout human history. The way people manage and use land resource is crucial to the social and economic well-being of peoples, as well as for its sustainability. Indian agriculture is undergoing technological transformation to ensure food security, export earnings and decentralized development to reduce rural poverty due to the increasing population pressure on the natural resource base of land, water, bio-diversity and other resources (Wani *et al.*, 2009).

Land provides basic necessities like food, clothing and shelter to human being. Land has always been an important locus for the economic activity necessary for human life. Any developmental activity is nearly impossible to conceive without taking land into consideration. The ability of land to provide space for production is limited by its physical and locational properties. Unlike goods, which can be moved around to where they are needed, land is immovable and cannot be physically passed by hand.

The term 'land use pattern' denotes the proportion of area under various types of uses, for example, the area actually cultivated, forest land, fallow land, pasture land, area under settlements and so on. The land use pattern in an area depends upon the physical and environmental factors as well as pressure of population on land. During the last two decades, India's population has increased by about 18.4 crores, while the total agricultural land has decreased by about 3.2 million hectares. According to Land Use Statistics of the Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India, a total agricultural land of nearly 3.16 million hectares (1.5 lakh ha per year) was lost to other sectors in the years between Triennium Ending (TE) 1991-92 and (TE) 2012-13 (Sharma, 2015). This investigation aims to examine shifts from one sector to another in land use patterns.

The study was focused to investigate shifts in land use from ecological and agricultural sectors to other sectors in Maharashtra state.

Data and methodology**Nature and sources of data**

The data used for the study was collected from various issues of Statistical Abstract of Maharashtra State, Handbook of Basic Statistics of Maharashtra State published by the Directorate of Economics and Statistics (DES), Government of Maharashtra, Mumbai. The time series data was obtained for a period of 57 years (1960-61 to 2016-17) which was further divided into two sub-periods as Period-I (Pre-liberalization) from 1960-61 to 1990-91 and Period-II (Post-liberalization) from 1991-92 to 2016-17 and also for the Overall time Period. The study was conducted to examine shifts in land use categories across Maharashtra state as a whole, as well as within its individual regions.

Ecological implications of land use dynamics

As per the methodology suggested by Pandey and Tewari (1987), Wani *et al.* (2009), Bardhan and Tewari (2010), Pushpa and Akashraj (2014) and Amale and Shiyani (2019), the total land endowment was conveniently grouped into three broad sectors, viz., (i) Ecological sector comprising forest, permanent pastures and other grazing lands, miscellaneous trees and groves which is not included in the net area sown and barren & uncultivable land (ii) Non-agricultural sector comprising area under non-agricultural uses, and (iii) Agricultural sector comprising cultivable wastes, net area sown, current fallow and fallows land other than current fallow. From this, the possible directions of major inter-sectoral as well as intra-sectoral land use shift were hypothesised.

Annual rate of change

The dynamics of land use shifts was examined with help of simple identity of linearly additive land-use changes. The first accounting identity was linearly sum up the area under all land-use classes which was equal to the total reported area, given by equation (1):

$$R = Fr + P + M + N + U + W + Fc + Fo + C \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where, R represents total reporting area, Fr the forest area, P the area under permanent pastures, M the area under miscellaneous tree crops, N the area under non-agricultural uses, U the barren and uncultivable lands, W the cultivable wastes, Fc the current fallows, Fo the fallows other than current fallow, C the net area sown.

Differentiating R with respect to time, we get
 $\Delta R = \Delta Fr + \Delta P + \Delta M + \Delta N + \Delta U + \Delta W + \Delta Fc + \Delta Fo + \Delta C$(2)

Where, Δ indicates change

The total land endowment can be conveniently grouped into three broad sectors, viz., (i) ecological sector (E) comprising Fr, P, M and U, (ii) agricultural sector (A) comprising W, C, Fc and Fo and (iii) non-agricultural (NA) sector. The ecological sector was further be divided into two sub sectors, viz., (i) the desirable ecology (E1) comprising Fr, P and M and (ii) undesirable ecology (E2) comprising U. Then, the net changes within each sector can be budgeted as,

$$\Delta E = \Delta E1 + \Delta E2 = (\Delta Fr + \Delta P + \Delta M) + (\Delta U)$$

..... (3)

$$\Delta A = \Delta Fc + \Delta Fo + \Delta W + \Delta C$$

..... (4)

As there is no possibility of land use shift from the non-agricultural sector to the agricultural sector, the net changes in the agricultural sector will have serious ecological implications. This net change, if positive (+ ΔA), will be at the cost of the ecological sector; if negative (- ΔA), the land use shift may occur to ecological or non-agricultural or both sectors, but definitely at the cost of the agricultural sector. In addition, the changes within the agricultural sector will also have some implications towards ecology and/or agricultural growth. The overall inter-sectoral land use transfers can be budgeted as:

$$\Delta R = \Delta E1 + \Delta E2 + \Delta A + \Delta N$$

.....(5)

For finding the annual rate of change in various land use classes, linear time trend equations were estimated on the land use time series data for the State. The annual rates of change for various classes were calculated using equations (3), (4), and (5), which aid in analysing the direction and dynamics of land use shifts.

Results and Discussion

Intra-sectoral dynamics of land use in Maharashtra

An attempt has been made to examine the absolute average annual changes in hectares terms in respect of each of the land use category for further budgeting of intra-sectoral land use shift. And inter-sectoral dynamics of land use in Maharashtra.

It could be ascertained from Table 3.1 and Figure 3.1 that during Period-I, land shifts have taken place from the forest, area under

Table 3.1. Intra-sectoral dynamics of land use in Maharashtra

Sr. No.	Land use sector	Land use category	Annual rate of change in '00' ha)		
			Period-I	Period-II	Overall
1	Non- agricultural	Land put to non-agricultural uses	136.93	204.19	168.16
2	Ecological	Forest	-0.30	-82.92	-38.66
		Miscellaneous tree crops and groves	-1.80	28.46	12.25
		Permanent pastures and other grazing land	25.90	-103.81	-34.32
		Barren and uncultivable land	-25.93	7.04	-10.63
3	Agricultural	Cultivable waste	31.97	-39.92	-1.41
		Current fallow	-107.37	202.69	36.59
		Fallow other than current fallow	-78.33	105.50	7.02
		Net area sown	20.63	-323.27	-139.04

Source: Authors' estimate

A comparative land use shift between Period-I and II indicated that the shifting rate of barren and uncultivable land to other land use categories has annually declined in Period-I (2,593 hectares) but it has increased in Period-II (704 hectares) in ecological sector. Similar observation was made in respect of current fallow and fallow other than current fallow in agricultural sector. Within agricultural sector, area under current fallow and fallow other than current fallow observed to be decreased by 10,737 and 7,833 hectares per annum, respectively during Period-I and it tilted towards increased by 20,269 and 10,550 hectares per annum, respectively during Period-II. On the contrary, cultivable waste and net area sown increased by annual change of 3,197 and 2,063 hectares, respectively during Period-I, however, this land use

miscellaneous tree crops and groves, as well as barren and uncultivable lands as an ecological sector to other sectors and it were declined annually by 30, 180 and 2,593 hectares, respectively. The permanent pastures and other grazing land was increased at an annual rate of 2,590 hectares during Period-I. In the agricultural sector, there was a shift in land from current fallow and fallow other than current fallow to other sub-sectors during Period-I. Here current fallow and fallow other than current fallow showed an annual decline by 10,737 and 7,833 hectares, respectively. The cultivable waste and net sown area increased at an annual rate of 3,197 and 2,063 hectares. However, in case of non-agricultural sector, there was substantial increase in the area with the annual rate of 13,693 hectares, at aggregate of Maharashtra state.

The results furnished in Table 3.1 and Figure 3.1 revealed that, during the Period-II, land shifts have taken place from permanent pastures and other grazing land and forest land as an ecological sector by 10,381 and 8,292 hectares to other sectors, respectively. However, barren and uncultivable lands and miscellaneous tree crops and groves have increased at an annual rate of 704 and 2,846 hectares, respectively. As, we concerned, annual rate of change, forest area declined within both the study periods and it is a sign of ecological degradation as the annual rate change was much higher (8292 ha/annum) during Period-II to that of Period-I (30 ha/annum). To maintain ecological balance and sustainability, the recommended share of forest to total geographical area is 33 per cent. To keep pace with the recommended level, the state has to initiate stiff actions and necessary policy provisions to restrain ecological imbalance.

In agricultural sector, there was a shift in area towards fallow other than current fallow and current fallow from the net area sown and cultivable waste land. The net area sown and cultivable waste land were decreased by 32,327 and 3,992 hectares per annum, however, current fallow and fallow other than current fallow lands has increased by 20,269 and 10,550 hectares per annum, respectively during Period-II. The non-agricultural sector showed an increase in its area by 20,419 hectares annually during this period against the annual increase of 13,693 hectares during Period-I. A relatively more increase in non-agricultural sector is unfavourable situation of land use. Since the land is limited to feed the millions of people in the country, its efficient use is utmost important.

categories were decreased by 3,992 and 32,327 hectares per annum, respectively in Period-II. This decline in net area sown is to be prime concern to researchers and policy makers.

For the Overall Period, it can be observed that land shift has taken place from the forest (3,866 hectares/annum), permanent pastures and other grazing lands (3,432 hectares/annum) and barren and uncultivable lands (1,063 hectares/annum) to another sector. Contrary, the area under miscellaneous tree crops and groves has increased at annual rate of 1,225 hectares. In agricultural sector, current fallow and fallow other than current fallow showed an annual increase of 3,659 and 702 hectares, respectively. At the level of Maharashtra state as a whole, cultivable waste land and net area sown have decreased

substantially at the annual rate of 141 and 13,904 hectares, respectively at Overall Period. However, area under non-agricultural sector showed

a considerable increase in its area to the extent of 16,816 hectares per annum at an aggregate of Maharashtra state.

Fig. 3.1 Intra-sectoral dynamics of land use in Maharashtra

Budgeting of inter-sectoral land use shift in Maharashtra

The sectoral annual rate of change, as given in Table 3.2 and Figure 3.2, reveals that during the Period-I, at the Maharashtra state as a whole, area under ecological sector declined minimal at an annual rate of 213 hectares. At aggregate of Maharashtra, the desirable ecology sector annually increased by 2,380 hectares while, the undesirable ecology sector decreased by 2,593 hectares indicating the favourable land use shift in both the sub-sectors of ecology sector. Agricultural sector showed a substantial decline of 13,310 hectares per annum. On the other hand, non-agricultural sector showed a sizable growth in area at the annual rate of 13,693 hectares.

During the Period-II, the area under ecological sector has substantially decreased at an annual rate of 15,123 hectares, of which, the desirable ecology was declined by 15,827 hectares, whereas, the undesirable ecological sector was increased by 704 hectares. This change was due to increase in barren and uncultivable land in recent years. Decline of desirable ecological sector during this period was due to the decline of permanent pastures and other grazing land and forest area in Maharashtra. The agricultural sector showed decline in area by 5,500 hectares annually, which was due to extremely decline in net area sown and cultivable waste land. On the other hand, non-agricultural sector showed an annual growth of 20,419 hectares during the Period-II.

During the Overall Period, the area under ecological sector has decreased at an annual rate of 7,136 hectares, of which, the share of desirable ecology was 6,073 hectares (85.10%) and the share of undesirable ecological sector was 1,063 hectares (14.90%). Decline of undesirable ecological sector during this period was due to the decline of area barren and uncultivable land in Maharashtra. The area under agricultural sector showed an annual decrease of 9,684 hectares while,

non-agricultural sector was annually increased by 16,816 hectares in the aforesaid period.

The comparative evaluation of land use shift between Period-I and Period-II indicates that, the area under ecological sector declined in both the periods, the rate of decline was more (15,123 hectares/annum) in Period-II over Period-I (213 hectares/annum). It is undesirable that the decline in area under ecological sector should be on account of tremendously decline in desirable ecology sector and the same was imitated during the Period-II. However, it is interesting to note that the scenario of area shifts under desirable ecology (E1) compared to undesirable ecology (E2) has not been favourable during Period-II and Overall Period, where land-use shift has been occurring from the desirable ecology towards either undesirable ecology and or non-agricultural sectors.

At the state level, inter-sectoral budgeting for Period-I and Period-II indicates that, though the area under agricultural sector declined in both the periods, it is desired that the rate of decline was less (55,00 hectares/annum) in Period-II over Period-I (13,310 hectares/annum). It is noticed that the decline in area under agricultural sector should be on account of equal or relatively more increased in area under non-agricultural sector and the same was reflected during the all three study periods. It is noteworthy to mention here that the land shift from the agricultural sector is due to decrease in either net area sown or fallow lands. This can be confirmed from the earlier discussion, perusal of Table 3.1, clearly depicted that agricultural sector showed declining trend throughout all study periods. This may be due to the undesirable land use categories of agricultural sector, which were declined during Period-I, eventually sole decrease in agriculture sector that was only due to the decrease in net area sown during Period-II and Overall Period.

Table 3.2. Budgeting of inter-sectoral land use shifts in Maharashtra

(Annual rate of change in '00' ha)

Sr. No.	Land use sector	Period-I	Period-II	Overall
1	Ecological ($\Delta E = \Delta E_1 + \Delta E_2$)	-2.13	-151.23	-71.36
	a. Desirable ecological (ΔE_1)	23.80	-158.27	-60.73
	b. Undesirable ecological (ΔE_2)	-25.93	7.04	-10.63
2	Agricultural (ΔA)	-133.10	-55.00	-96.84
3	Non-agricultural (ΔN)	136.93	204.19	168.16
4	Net sectoral changes	1.70	-2.04	-0.04

Source: Authors' estimate

Note : The net sectoral change is equal to algebraic sum of $\Delta N + \Delta E_1 + \Delta E_2 + \Delta A$

Against the constant growth of area under non-agricultural sector at the Maharashtra has experienced one-and-a-half times more annual increase in area under non-agricultural sector during Period-II (20,419 hectares/annum) over Period-I (13,693 hectares/annum). This was reflected that prominently agricultural land converted into non-

agricultural uses during post liberalization period in Maharashtra. It may be noted from the analysis that at the state level, the net sectoral change during all the periods considered for the analysis has turned out to be positive. This type of phenomenon is not unique to present study.

Fig. 3.2. Inter-sectoral land use shifts in Maharashtra

Region wise budgeting of inter-sectoral land use shifts in Maharashtra

The regionwise inter-sectoral land use shift experienced in Maharashtra during the periods under study has been estimated and the results are presented in Table 3.3, which are discussed in this section from ecological implications point of view.

During the Period-I, except Vidarbha region, all regions of Maharashtra showed an increase in the area under ecological sector among which, Marathwada region witnessed highest magnitude of annual increase to the extent of 1,983 hectares in area under ecology sector due to the result of increase in the area under desirable ecological sector (1,317 hectares/annum) and undesirable ecological sector (667 hectares/annum). Area under ecological sector has declined substantially in the Vidarbha region of Maharashtra at an annual rate of 5,797 hectares, out of which the share of desirable ecology was 3,637 hectares (62.74%) and the share of undesirable ecological sector was 2,160 hectares (37.26%). The declining rate in case of Vidarbha region may be due to the fact that area under permanent pasture and other grazing land (desirable ecological sector) and barren and uncultivable land (undesirable ecological sector) decreased by very high magnitude with tune of 2,300 and 2,160 hectares per annum, respectively in this region. This may be converted to agricultural purposes or non-agricultural uses also, during the Period-I.

During Period-II, all the regions of Maharashtra experienced the decline in area under ecological sector. The annual rate of decline was the highest in Vidarbha region with the magnitude of 8,069 hectares per annum, followed by Western Maharashtra, Marathwada and Konkan regions of Maharashtra. For the Overall Period, mixed trend observed, where Konkan and Marathwada regions of Maharashtra showed an increase in area under ecological sector, whereas, Western Maharashtra and Vidarbha regions showed a decline in area under ecological sector indicating the need of efforts to check decline in desirable ecological sector i.e., forest, permanent pastures and other grazing lands and area under miscellaneous trees and groves. Policy makers should pay due attention for restructuring of land acquisition policies to bring more of the undesirable ecological sectors' land for development, sparing desirable ecological sector.

If we consider the sub-sectors of the ecological sector of land use i.e., desirable and undesirable ecological sectors separately during all periods of study, it has been seen that area under undesirable ecological

sector declined in Konkan and Western Maharashtra regions, whereas, Marathwada region of Maharashtra showed an increase in undesirable ecology. On the other hand, the desirable ecological sector was increased in Konkan region, while, Vidarbha region was showed decline in desirable ecology sector. The favorable situation from ecological point of view was observed in case of Konkan region during all the three study periods, where area under desirable ecological sector increased by 2,490, 615 and 1,620 hectares per annum and undesirable ecological sector was decreased by 740, 850 and 791 hectares per annum during the Period-I, Period-II and Overall Period, respectively.

Also, in case of Western Maharashtra region, favorable situation with outlook of the ecological point was observed during Period-I. Where, area under desirable ecological sector increased by 2,210 hectares per annum, however, undesirable ecological sector was decreased by 360 hectares per annum during the Period-I. On the flip side, unfavorable ecological situation in Vidarbha region was noticed during Period-II, in which area under desirable ecological sector declined by 9,681 hectares per annum and area under undesirable ecological sector increased was by 1,612 hectares per annum and in Marathwada region area under desirable ecological sector declined by 1,785 and 123 hectares per annum and area under undesirable ecological sector increased was by 396 and 541 hectares per annum during Period-II and Overall Period, respectively.

Area under agricultural sector has decreased in all regions except, Vidarbha region during all the three study periods. Agricultural sector was increased by 2,243, 3,254 and 2,713 hectares per annum during Period-I, Period-II and Overall Period, respectively in Vidarbha region of Maharashtra. This very high rate of increase in Vidarbha region was due to the fact that agricultural sector includes cultivable waste and fallow lands also. Contrary, the regions of Konkan, Western Maharashtra and Marathwada experienced the shift of land from agricultural sector to the other sectors during all study periods. The highest magnitude of decline in agricultural sector was to be found in Western Maharashtra region with the tune of 6,240, 5,873 and 6,070 hectares per annum during Period-I, Period-II and Overall Period, respectively. Further, it may be noted from the results that during Period-II, Western Maharashtra and Marathwada regions have showed decrease in area under agricultural sector which might be the impact of low rainfall in the respective regions of Maharashtra.

Table 3.3. Regionwise budgeting of inter-sectoral land use shifts in Maharashtra

Sr. No.	Land use sector	Annual rate of change ('00' ha)					
		Konkan			Western Maharashtra		
		Period-I	Period-II	Overall	Period-I	Period-II	Overall
1.	Ecological ($\Delta E = \Delta E_1 + \Delta E_2$)	17.50	-2.35	8.29	18.50	-54.31	-15.30
a.	Desirable ecological (ΔE_1)	24.90	6.15	16.20	22.10	-49.77	-11.27
b.	Undesirable ecological (ΔE_2)	-7.40	-8.50	-7.91	-3.60	-4.54	-4.04
2.	Agricultural (ΔA)	-57.37	-18.85	-39.48	-62.40	-58.73	-60.70
3.	Non-agricultural (ΔN)	41.53	21.15	32.07	45.03	112.92	76.55

4.	Net sectoral changes	1.67	-0.04	0.88	1.13	-0.12	0.55
		Marathwada			Vidarbha		
1.	Ecological ($\Delta E = \Delta E_1 + \Delta E_2$)	19.83	-13.88	4.18	-57.97	-80.69	-68.52
a.	Desirable ecological (ΔE_1)	13.17	-17.85	-1.23	-36.37	-96.81	-64.43
b.	Undesirable ecological (ΔE_2)	6.67	3.96	5.41	-21.60	16.12	-4.09
2.	Agricultural(ΔA)	-35.77	-9.96	-23.79	22.43	32.54	27.13
3.	Non-agricultural(ΔN)	15.83	23.83	19.55	34.53	46.27	39.98
4.	Net sectoral changes	-0.10	0.00	-0.05	-1.00	-1.88	-1.41

Source: Authors' estimate

Note: The net sectoral change is equal to algebraic sum of $\Delta N + \Delta E_1 + \Delta E_2 + \Delta A$

Area under non-agricultural sector has showed an increase in all the regions and during all three study periods. Where, the magnitude of annual rate of increase was the highest in Period-II as compared to Period-I in all regions of Maharashtra, except Konkan region, because of the fact that the most of the infrastructural developments were planned in the Period-II like major irrigation dams, power projects, national as well as state highways, etc. It was concluded that in all regions of Maharashtra state, area under non-agricultural use has increased.

Conclusions and policy implications-

At the overall level, the outcome of ecological implication in Maharashtra revealed that the ecological sector was declined due to the desirable ecology sector has been decreased, which includes area under forest and permanent pastures and other grazing lands and it is a sign of ecological degradation. While, the area under the agricultural sector annually decreased by 9,684 hectares due to a declined the net area sown and cultivable wasteland and the same situation was found in Period -II. The findings of ecological study in Maharashtra exhibited that the undesirable ecological sector had increased by 704 hectares per annum during Period II, which was primarily due to the expansion of barren and uncultivable land in the state.

The shift of area from desirable to undesirable ecological sector may have long term negative environmental implications. So, integration of agricultural and rural development programmes viz; National Horticulture Mission, National Bamboo Mission, MNREGA etc. are necessary to make the use of barren and uncultivable land for cultivation, for holistic rural development, natural resource management and eco-restoration. The unfavorable trend of desirable ecological sector and the vicious land use dynamics lead to the degeneration of this important natural resource, which is a matter of grave concern and needs to be managed on priority basis with efforts from all the stakeholders, particularly policy makers in changing agro-ecological situations to minimize the effects of climate change.

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